

IQTISODIY TERMINLARNING STRUKTURAVIY VA SEMANTIK TAHLILI

Mansurova Nodira Anvaronva

Toshkent moliya instituti, "Xorijiy tillar" kafedrasida katta o'qituvchisi

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Annotatsiya. Maqola iqtisodiy terminologiyaning struktur va semantik tahliliga bag'ishlangan. Unda terminlar turlari va ularni ko'rsatishning asosiy tarkibiy usullari aks ettirilgan. Shuningdek, terminlarning tuzilishi va asosiy leksik birliklari tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: strukturaviy-semantik tahlil, terminologik modellar, bir so'zli terminlar, semantik hosila, kompozitsion modellar, ko'p komponentli terminlar.

СТРУКТУРНО-СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ ТЕРМИНОВ

Аннотация. Статья посвящена структурно-семантическому анализу экономической терминологии. В ней отражены виды терминов и основные структурные способы их представления. Также анализируется структура терминов и основных лексических единиц.

Ключевые слова: структурно-семантический анализ, терминологические модели, однословные термины, семантическая деривация, композиционные модели, многокомпонентные термины.

STRUCTURAL AND SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF ECONOMIC TERMS

Abstract. The article is devoted to the structural-semantic analysis of economic terminology. It reflects the types of terms and the main structural ways of their presentation. The structure of terms and basic lexical units is also analyzed.

Keywords: structural-semantic analysis, terminological models, one-word terms, semantic derivation, compositional models, multicomponent terms.

KIRISH

Tadqiqotimizda biz iqtisodiy terminni birlik sifatida ko'rib chiqamiz. Leksik birliklar terminlar, professionalizmlar, eponimlar, jargon ("qisqartirilgan uslub leksikasi"), qisqartmalar va umumiy ilmiy nifon nifon rdslardan tashkil topgan noterminologik leksika bilan ifodalanadi.

TADQIQOT MATERIALLARI VA METODOLOGIYASI

Iqtisodiyotga oid terminlarni tahlil qilish jarayonida terminlarning quyidagi turlari aniqlandi:

- iqtisodiy terminlar: *assets, liabilities, investor capital, accountability, target market, growth cycle, expense, liquidity, financial management, target market, balance sheet, income, treasury securities, credit, stock market, share, trade deficit, corporate management, fund, investment policy, economy system, dividend, clearing bank, tax, gross profit, joint venture, cash flow, stakeholder, value added tax*, va boshqalar..

- huquqiy terminlar: *plaintiff, lawsuit, litigation matter, sanction, imprisonment, judgment, crime, legislation, pending litigation, fiduciary duty, regulation, pact, copyrights, piracy, intellectual property*, va boshqalar.

Ijtimoiy sohaga oid terminlar: *interpersonal communication, population, culture, public, social system, demography, birthrate, labor units, strike, behavior, survival rate, gender gap*, va boshqalar.

- Texnologiyaga sohaga oid terminlar: *machine, tool, engine, equipment, semiconductor, trailer-mounted system*, va boshqalar.

– Siyosatshunoslik terminlari: *democracy, socialism, communism, 21st century capitalism, political contest, democracy, seismic political change*, va boshqalar..

- Ta'lim sohasiga oid terminlar: *graduate, student, profession, education, preparatory school, mid-level institution, faculty, nurse-educator, tuition, mathematics, diploma, school, faculty*, va boshqalar.

Affiksial so'z yasaliş modellari:

- prefiksatsiya modellari: *reconciliation, reassignment, reimbursement, restatement, unavailability, unfunded, unbalance, undiscounted, underpayment, multibuyer, multicurrency, inpayment, inconvertibility, co-creditor, co-debtor, cooperation, ex-dividend, exchange, hypermarket, hyperinflation* va boshqalar.

TADVIQOT NATIJALARI

Prefikslar o'rganilayotgan terminologiyani chiqarishda muhim rol o'ynaydi, ular boshlang'ich tuzilmani, masalan, "hodisalar va tushunchalar" salbiy toifasini belgilash uchun ishlatiladi: *unemployment (the model bears value of "lack of work"), nonpayment (the model bears value of "lack of payment")*.

Co- prefiksini qo'llash boshqaruv sohasida mavjud derivatsion terminlarning so'z yasaliş modellarida uchrash mumkin, masalan,: *cooperation, coordination, co-management*; - harakatni birgalikda amalga oshirish ma'nosiga ega.

Re- prefiksi juda tez qo'llaniladi va takroriy harakatni ifodalaydi (*restatement – repeated submission of financial statements, reconciliation – coordination, verification of accounts; reimbursement – compensation*).

Multi - hajm, ko'pplik" - ma'nosini anglatadi (multinational – multinational company).

Un – negative, salbiy ma'noni ifodalaydi "kamchilik yoki biror narsaning yo'qligi": *unavailability – absence of availability; unbalance – discrepancy*.

– qo'shimchalar yordamida tuzilgan terminlar: *settlement, investor, accounting, accountability, marketing, management, financial, planner, discounter, competitiveness, recruiting, corporation, reporting, economist, managerial, economic, entrepreneurial, organizational, monopolistic, compensation, negotiation*, va boshqalar.

Iqtisodiy sohaga oid o'rganilayotgan terminologiyani shakllantirishda eng ko'p ishlatiladigan qo'shimchalar quyidagilardir:

- er/or (discounter, distributor),
- ion (commodization, corporation),
- ing (accounting),
- ic (economic),
- ant (accountant),
- ment (management),
- able (marketable),
- ive (competitive),
- al (entrepreneurial, beneficial),
- ship (partnership).

MUHOKAMA

Tahlillar derivatsion oilaga tegishli terminlarni ko'rsatadi: *manage, manager, management, managerial; invest, investor, investment; account, accountant, accountability, accounting*, va boshqalar. Bunday hosilalar va qo'shma atamalarning semantikasi kompozit

bo'lib, turli kasbiy toifalarni aks ettiradi, masalan: manage – category of management process, manager – category of the subject, management – category of economic area. Composition models: cross-marketing, marketplace, world-changing, stakeholder, risk-management, salespeople, headquarter, trademark, businessman, union-management, community-based organization, home-based business, va boshqalar.

Asosiy tarkibi mustaqil so'zga teng bo'lgan kompozit modellar termin hosil qilishning samarali usuli bo'lib, u turli xil bilim sohalari tushunchalarini bitta matnda birlashtirishga imkon beradi. Iqtisodiy terminologiyadagi iboralar quyidagi modellar bo'yicha tuzilgan: N+N; Adj+N; Ving +N; (Adj, V-ing)+N. Iqtisodiy nutqdagi terminlarning ko'p sonini ikkilik terminli iboralar tashkil qiladi (1126 birlik): *institutional investor, financial management, financial state, consumer loyalty, consumer acquisition, consumer detention, selling innovations, practice of business relations, selling skills, the target market, the control tool, management institution, market statistic, junk bond, multinational corporation, economic forces, entrepreneurial leader, economic world, national economy, economic power, economic game, service sales, commercial risk, letter of credit, transparent export, international trade, corporate entity, balance of payment, annual growth, market research, primary business, specific market, manufacturing transfer, joint venture, offshore partner, labor shortage, independent business, leading firm, trading firm, economic development, business community, economic motivation, entrepreneurial institution, export strategy, treatment management, organizational management, export opportunity, consume resources, benefit package, deal breaker, supplier partnership, contract fulfillment, purchasing departments, manufacturing/delivery process, marketing opportunity, development costs, non-competitive plant, product line, financial image, brokerage house, financial foundation, fiscal year, cash leaks, business formation*, va boshqalar.

Bunday terminologik iboralar kontseptual mazmuni ifodalash uchun bir so'zli atamalarga qaraganda ko'proq imkoniyatlarga ega. Quyidagi qism - 173 terminologik birlik - ko'p komponentli terminlardan iborat. (To'rt so'z va dengizdan iborat uch so'z atama va atamalar). Ko'p komponentli atamalar quyidagi strukturaviy modellar bo'yicha taqsimlanadi: 1) Adj +N + N (*recruiting boom cycle, financial service firm, mutual fund owner, absolute cost advantage, overall market strategy, actual product performance, current business crunch*); 2) Adj + Adj +N (*unipolar economic world, substantial secondary market, low direct expenses, severe economic pressure*); 3) N+N+N (*exchange rate guarantees, vendor selection process, bed-andbreakfast venture, product development group, job share team, database management system, non-profit subsidiary corporation*); 4) Adj + (Adj, V-ing) +N (*financial reporting period, collaborative working partnership, ideal marketing strategy, daily trading limit*); 5) Adj+ N +N+N (*common market entry strategy, accrual basis income statement*); 6) (V-ed, Adj)+(V-ing, Adj)+N (*non-employed working style, self-employed working style*); 7) (V-ed, Adj)+Adj+(V-ing, Adj)+N (*detailed realistic marketing plan*); 8) (V-ed, Adj) +N + Adj (*accrued taxes payable*); 9) Adj +N+ Adj + N +N (*global network discriminatory tax policy*); 10) Adj + Adj + N +N (*strategic financial management issues*); 11) Adj + Adj + Adj +N (*chief strategic financial planner*); 12) N to N +(V-ing, Adj)+N (*face-to-face working meeting*).

Ikki, uch va undan ortiq komponentli terminlarning yig'indisi emas, balki nominativ kompleksni tashkil etuvchi har bir komponentning qiymatini aks ettiradi, lekin kognitiv jarayonning integratsiyalashuvi natijasi bunday kompozit ma'noni shakllantirishda sodir bo'ladi. Shuni qo'shimcha qilish kerakki, qisqartmalar (95 birlik) iqtisodiy kompyuter nutqida muhim rol

o'ynaydi va ularni 2 guruhga bo'lish mumkin: 1. Terminologik qisqartmalar. Misol uchun: GAAT (General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade), WTO (the World Trade Organization), NASA (Newspaper Advertising Sales Association), UAW (United Auto Workers), GM (General Motors), SBA (Small Business Administration), OEM (Original Equipment Manufacturer). 2. Umumiy qisqartmalar, masalan ASAP (as soon as possible), IMHO (in my humble/honest opinion). Iqtisodiy sohada qisqartmalardan foydalanish til iqtisodiyoti maqsadi bilan bir qatorda, registratning joy va vaqtini saqlash va ekonomiya maqsadini ham ko'zlaydi. Iqtisodiyotda atama shakllanishining yana bir o'ziga xos xususiyati semantik hosiladir.

XULOSA

Tahlil bir qancha leksik birliklarni ko'rsatdiki, ular qo'llanilayotgan kommunikativ muhitga va u erda o'ynashi kerak bo'lgan rolga qarab, turli xil bo'lishi mumkin. Tahlil shuni ko'rsatdiki, forumlarning iqtisodiy nutqi shartlarining eng katta qismi asosiy tushunchalar va kategoriyalarni aks ettiruvchi iqtisodiy atamalarga tegishli (iqtisod, menagement, , buxgalteriya hisobi va boshqalar). Xulosa o'rnida shuni ta'kidlash joizki, noterminologik leksika turli ilmiy sohalar atamaları bilan bir qatorda iqtisodiy nutqda ham muhim o'rin tutadi. Terminologik bo'lmagan birliklar manzil shakli sifatida nutq, funktsiyani yaratishga yordam beradi (siz e'tibor berganingizdek va hokazo), nutqning mantiqiy tuzilishini shakllantirishga yordam beradi. Bunday birliklar shartlar bo'yicha erishib bo'lmaydigan, lekin muvaffaqiyatli kommunikativ harakatni shakllantirish va rivojlantirish uchun zarur bo'lgan vazifalarni bajaradi, nutqda so'z bilan ifodalanadi.

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